

Efficient and Compact Face Descriptor for Driver Drowsiness Detection

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Abstract

Current advances in driver drowsiness detection consist of a variety of innovative technologies generally based on driver state monitoring systems. Extracting effective and relevant features to characterize drowsy symptoms in images and videos is still an open topic. In this work, we introduce a face monitoring system based on a compact face texture descriptor able to cover the most discriminant drowsy features. The compactness has been achieved by both a multi-scale pyramidal face representation that capture the main characteristics of local and global information, and the feature selection process applied on the raw extracted features. The proposed framework is rolled out in four phases: (i) face detection and alignment; (ii) Pyramid-Multi Level (PML) face representation; (iii) face description using a multi-level multi scale feature extraction; and (vi) feature subset selection and classification. Experiments conducted on the public dataset NTH Drowsy Driver Detection (NTHUDDD) show the effectiveness of the proposed face descriptor and the associated selection schemes. The results show that the proposed method compares favorably with several approaches including those based on deep Convolutional Neural Networks.

Keywords: Drowsiness detection, hand-crafted features, deep features, face image analysis.

1 Introduction

Motivated by the need to limit the number of drowsy driving related crashes with the automobile industry’s migration towards effective safety technologies, the global market for drowsiness monitoring systems is projected to reach US\$4.2 billion by 2024. During the last decade, many drowsiness detection systems have been proposed. These can be grouped in three categories (Azim et al., 2014; Colic et al., 2014; Sigari et al., 2014). The first

category relies on using some physiological data collected from a wide variety of sources like electrocardiogram (ECG), electroencephalogram (EEG), or sphygmomanometer (Awais et al., 2017). The second category, however, focuses on the driver status as well as on the interaction between the vehicle and the driver, including the force of the driver’s grip on the steering wheel, braking, acceleration, and speed. Finally, the last category makes use of machine vision approaches in order to monitor the driver’s status using cameras and optical sensors (Sigari, 2009; Omidyeganeh et al., 2016; Gilbile et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2017).

Although the detection systems which fall under the first category can provide high-performance recognition, their use is limited because of their intrusive character. While the second group of approaches can be non-intrusive, they are constrained by several limitations that may include the type of the vehicle, the external conditions, and the driver experience. Therefore, computer vision technology seems to provide non-invasive solutions with few limitations to deal with this problem.

In the present work, we are interested in computer vision based systems. These include eye-tracking systems to monitor driver fatigue; forwarding looking cameras to monitor driving patterns (speed, steering movements, drifting between traffic lanes) and face monitoring systems to track drowsy symptoms related facial expressions (yawning, head or body nodding, difficulty keeping eyes open).

Recent drowsy driver detection systems mainly are based on a limited number of visual indicators. In (Kumar and Barwar, 2014; Alioua et al., 2014; Bandara, 2006; Sigari, 2009), for example, the vision-based driver fatigue detection systems were built focusing only on features of eyes or mouth. The extracted features could not well encode the state of driver drowsiness because of the complexity of the drowsiness state which corresponds to constant and fast blinking, yawning, nodding or head swinging. In addition, these techniques entirely depend on an accurate and good detection of the mouth and eyes, which can be very difficult in the real-life condition. Indeed, some limitations of these systems have already been raised in the literature. Teyeb et al. (Teyeb et al., 2014) showed that the level of alertness of the driver decreases as the head inclination angle is greater than a given threshold and its duration exceeds a given value. In (Alioua et al., 2014), yawning is detected by using the variation rate of the mouth contour. It is assumed to be the only symptom of drowsiness which may lead to some false alarms, specially, for cases in which the required visual observations are very challenging to be distinguished from other similar movements, e.g. laughing or talking. In (Choi et al., 2016), the authors proposed a method

that detects the gaze region using features provided by a convolutional neural network. The region of the driver gaze is then estimated using support vector machine (SVM) classifier. In addition to the above techniques, some works exploited the texture dynamics in the sequence of images (Arashloo and Kittler, 2014; Päivärinta et al., 2011; Zhao and Pietikainen, 2007; Niu and Wang, 2014).

In this work, we propose a face monitoring system based on a hand-crafted face descriptor extracted from different image regions at different scales adopting a pyramidal structure. The final face descriptor is then given by concatenating all individual descriptors over all regions. As stated previously, our proposed system develops in four main phases: (i) face detection and alignment; (ii) Pyramid-Multi Level (PML) face representation; (iii) face description using a multi-level multi scale feature extraction; and (vi) feature subset selection and classification. The main goal is to perform a binary classification of static images in order to identify the driver status: drowsy or not drowsy.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 briefly describes the adopted 2D face alignment and cropping. Section 3 presents in details the proposed descriptor. Section 4 presents some experimental results obtained with the public database Drowsy Driver Detection. Section 5 provide a short conclusion.

2 Face descriptors: Background

In this section, we review the main properties of the three descriptors considered in this work, namely, the histogram of oriented gradients (HOG) features, the Covariance descriptor (COV) and the classical texture local binary pattern (LBP) features. The description of the different modules characterizing each of these descriptors are illustrated in Figure 1.

2.1 Histogram of Oriented Gradients descriptor

Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG)(Dalal and Triggs, 2005) is a feature descriptor that rely on the number of occurrences of gradient orientation in localized portions of an image - cells and blocks. The main idea is that local shape information can be characterized using the distribution of local intensity gradients. As it can be see in Figure 1(A), the image region is divided into small overlapping spatial regions or *cells*. Then, for each cell the 1-D histogram of gradient orientation is accumulated over all the pixels in the cell. This creates the descriptor of the cell. The HOG descriptor of the

image is formed by the combination of the descriptors of the cells. The most important parameters for the HOG descriptor are the number of orientation histogram bins (NumBins), the number of cells in a block (BlockSize) and the size of HOG cells (CellSize). Tuning these parameters, we can encode finer orientation details, capture large-scale spatial information, or capture the significance of local pixels. The setting of these parameters is reported in Experimental Setup Section.

2.2 Covariance descriptor

This descriptor was originally proposed for object detection and texture classification tasks (Tuzel et al., 2006). Instead of using histograms, the work of (Tuzel et al., 2006) calculates the covariance matrices associated with the gradient images and color channels. The covariance descriptor provides a relatively compact descriptor given the fact it is a hybrid descriptor that allows a natural way of fusing multiple types of features as long as they can be presented by maps. This descriptor can benefit from the advances that can be made in image feature extraction. Besides, this descriptor allows efficient implementation since very often the image regions are rectangular. This is achieved by exploiting the concept of integral image (Tuzel et al., 2006).

This descriptor is computed as follows: let R denote a $M \times N$ intensity image region, and V be the set of the $M \times N \times d$ dimensional feature images extracted from I (see Figure 1(B) for a graphical illustration). Thus, V can be seen as a set of d 2D arrays (channels) where every array corresponds to a given image feature such as horizontal coordinate, vertical coordinate, color, image derivatives, and filter responses, etc. This multi-dimensional array can be written as $V(x; y) = \phi(I; x; y)$ where ϕ is a function that extracts image features.

For a given image region $\mathcal{R} \in I$ containing n pixels, let $\{\mathbf{v}_i\}_{i=1\dots n}$ denote the d -dimensional feature vectors obtained by ϕ within \mathcal{R} . According to (Tuzel et al., 2006), the region \mathcal{R} can be described by a $d \times d$ covariance matrix:

$$\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{R}} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (\mathbf{v}_i - \bar{\mathbf{v}})(\mathbf{v}_i - \bar{\mathbf{v}})^T, \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{v}}$ is the mean vector of $\{\mathbf{v}_i\}_{i=1\dots n}$. The sample covariance matrix, \mathcal{S} , represents the second order statistics of the d dimensional vectors $\{\mathbf{v}_i\}$ within the region \mathcal{R} .

For a given number of channels, d , it follows that the covariance descriptor of each region is described by $(d \times (d - 1)/2)$ features. For a detailed and formal description of this descriptor we refer the reader to (Moujahid and Dornaika, 2019b; Moujahid and Dornaika, 2019a).

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the different features extraction algorithms adopted in this work. **(A) The HOG descriptor** (Adaptation from (Ma et al., 2016)): in this illustration, the gradient orientations corresponds to an image region with 8×8 cells, each cell of size 4×4 pixels, and a local histogram with 9 orientations (bins) and with a 1-by-1 cell overlap between blocks. **(B) The COV descriptor**: The input image region is represented by a set of d texture and color features that will be used to construct the feature sample matrix. The final covariance descriptor is then computed as the logarithm of the covariance matrix. **(C) The basic LBP operator** (from (Kabbai et al., 2015)): The central pixel with value 12 in the 3×3 image is replaced by the binary code $10100001 = 128$. By applying this operation on the pixels of the original image, the latter is transformed to a LBP image. The histogram of the LBP image gives the LBP histogram.

2.3 Local Binary Patterns (LBP) descriptor

Local binary pattern (LBP) descriptor gives an efficient way to capture local structures of an input image by comparing each pixel with its neighbors. The most important properties of LBP are its tolerance regarding monotonic illumination changes and its computational simplicity. The original LBP operator replaces the value of the pixels of an image with decimal numbers, which are called LBPs or LBP codes that encode the local structure around each pixel (Ahonen et al., 2006). It proceeds thus, as illustrated in Figure 1(C). Each central pixel is compared with its eight neighbors; the neighbors having smaller value than that of the central pixel will have the bit 0, and the other neighbors having value equal to or greater than that of the central pixel will have the bit 1. For each given central pixel, one can generate a binary number that is obtained by concatenating all these binary bits in a clockwise direction, which starts from the one of its top-left neighbor. The resulting decimal value of the generated binary number replaces the central pixel value. The histogram of LBP labels (the frequency of occurrence of each code) calculated over a region or an image can be used as a texture descriptor of that image.

3 The proposed scheme: description of the different modules

Figure 2 illustrates the flowchart of our proposed scheme that consists of a chain of processing modules arranged so that the output of each module represents the input of the next one. Five main modules can be raised: (i) face detection and alignment; (ii) Pyramid Multi-level (PML) face representation; (iii) PML feature extraction; (iv) dimensionality reduction (PCA) and subset feature selection (Fisher score); and finally (v) SVM-based classification strategy.

3.1 Face detection and alignment

Face registration is one of the most important pre-processing steps in face image analysis. We proceed as follows. First, the 2D location of the eyes of each face are determined using the Ensemble of Regression Trees (ERT) algorithm (Kazemi and Sullivan, 2014). This is an efficient and robust algorithm for facial landmarks detection.

Once the 2D locations of the two eyes is known, we utilize them to compensate for the image rotation of the face. To this end, within the

Figure 2: A schematic representation of data flow for drowsines detection in individual video frames.

detected face region, the right and left eyes are located as (R_x, R_y) and (L_x, L_y) , respectively. The in-plane rotation angle is calculated by $\theta = \text{artan}(\frac{R_y - L_y}{R_x - L_x})$, and the input face region is rotated by the that angle.

After rotation correction, we use a global scale for the face image, this scale normalizes the inter-ocular distance to a fixed value l . The latter sets the scale of the face in the obtained image. After performing the rotation and scaling, the face zone should be cropped in order to obtained an aligned face. To this end, a bounding box is anchored on the new eyes location. Thus, the left (right) vertical boundary is set at a distance of $k_0 \cdot l$ from the left (right) eye.

The top boundary is set at a distance of $k_1 \cdot l$ from the vertical position of the horizontal eyes. The bottom boundary is set at a distance of $k_1 \cdot l$.

In our work, k_0 , k_1 , k_2 and l are selected such that the final cropped face has a size of 250×250 pixels.

3.2 Pyramid Multi-Level (PML) face representation

The PML representation relies on an explicit pyramid representation allowing a multi-scale exploration of the original image. At each scale, a multi-block representation is performed. The descriptor of each resulting

block is then extracted using the steps described in Figure 1.

For a pyramid of ℓ levels, and considering individual square blocks of size $(b \times b)$ pixels, the size of the image at level i is then given by $i \times (b, b)$. The total number of blocks is given by $T = \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} i^2 = \ell(\ell + 1)(2\ell + 1)/6$. At level 1 (the top of the pyramid), the whole image is reduced to one single block of $b \times b$ pixels.

Formally, the PML representation of the image is built as follows: Let f be an image of size $N \times N$. Let P be its pyramid representation with ℓ levels, $P = \{L_1, \dots, L_\ell\}$ (Szeliski, 2011). The size of the images L_i should meet the following. Each level L_i is represented by a partition of square blocks of size $\frac{N}{\ell} \times \frac{N}{\ell}$, $L_i = \{B_{i,1}, \dots, B_{i,n_i}\}$, where $n_i = i^2$. Given a value ℓ , we pose $b = \frac{N}{\ell}$. Thus, the size of square blocks at all levels is $b \times b$. We point out that P_ℓ is f and $P_1 = B_{1,1}$ (coarsest resolution).

The pyramid representation of an image f by ℓ levels is the sequence L_1, \dots, L_ℓ such that:

$$L_i = \{B_{i,1}, \dots, B_{i,n_i}\} \quad \text{where } i = 1, \dots, \ell \quad \text{and } n_i = i^2 \quad (2)$$

3.3 PML face descriptor

Once the PML representation is obtained, the local features of each block at each level are described by the selected descriptor (HOG, COV or LBP). At level i ($i = 1, \dots, \ell$) the associated PML descriptor is given by:

$$\text{Descriptor}(L_i) = \text{Descriptor}(B_{i,1}) \parallel \dots \parallel \text{Descriptor}(B_{i,n_i})$$

where \parallel is the concatenation operator. Thus, the face PML Descriptor adoting ℓ levels has the following expression:

$$\ell\text{-PMLD}(f) = \text{Descriptor}(L_1) \parallel \dots \parallel \text{Descriptor}(L_\ell) \quad (3)$$

As it can be seen in Table 2, for a pyramid with depth ℓ , the total number of blocks is $T = \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} i^2 = \frac{\ell(\ell+1)(2\ell+1)}{6}$. Therefore, ℓ -PMLD is given by $\frac{\ell(\ell+1)(2\ell+1)D}{6}$ elements, where D refers to the number of elements in the individual descriptor.

3.4 Feature processing and classification

As reported previously, the PML descriptor is obtained by concatenating all individual descriptors corresponding to each block at each level of the pyramid. This final descriptor is associated with all resolutions and all image

parts, and may result in a high-dimensional descriptor which may contain a lot of redundant and unreliable information. In data mining, it is well known that feature selection can avoid, on one hand, over-fitting problems while improving classification model performance, and on the other hand, to provide efficient and more cost-effective learning models (Guan et al., 2014).

In this work, we used Fisher score method (Gu et al., 2012) in order to retrieve the most discriminative and relevant features of the generated PML-based descriptors. Before carrying out this step, we projected the data into a reduced space using principal component analysis (PCA). Finally, the classification of the input is performed using a non-linear SVM classifier.

4 Experimental setup

4.1 Dataset

In this work, we used the driver drowsiness video dataset collected by NTHU Computer Vision Lab (Park et al., 2017). To the best of our knowledge, this is the only available public dataset which contains a large number of image frames. This video dataset contains 36 subjects of different ethnicities recorded with and without wearing glasses/sunglasses under a variety of simulated driving scenarios, including normal driving, yawning, slow blink rate, falling asleep, burst out laughing, etc., under day and night illumination conditions.

The total dataset is divided into training, evaluation and test sets. The training set consists of 360 video clips (722, 223 frames) corresponding to 18 subjects. The evaluation set comprises 20 video clips (173, 259 frames) of 4 subjects, and the test set consists of 70 clips (736, 132 frames) of 14 subjects. Images in the training and evaluation sets are binary labeled as drowsy or non drowsy.

The ground-truth labels for test set are not publicly available yet. The dataset includes different physical attributes including variety in skin tone, fatigue, facial structure, clothes and hair styles. The videos are in 640×480 pixels, 30 frames per second AVI format without audio. Figures 3 and 4 show respectively images from the same situation (night bareface) and different status, and the same status but at different situations.

The videos in each situation of the training set are divided into 4 categories according to the subject’s states: *non drowsy*, *drowsy*, *yawning* and *head nodding*. In this work, the last three states are used to represent the *drowsy class*. Table 1 shows how the images are distributed per situation for both training and validation sets.

Figure 3: Example frames of same situation (night bareface) and different behaviors (mixing drowsy and non-drowsy state) from one video clip (Park et al., 2017).

Figure 4: Some examples of different situations (night wearing glasses, night bareface, wearing glasses, wearing sunglasses, bareface) and same status (drowsy state) from five video sequences (Park et al., 2017)

The training set has been sub-sampled at a 1/10th rate to reduce the training data size. After the sub-sampling process, all frames that do not have a matching positive label in the face detected list have been removed.

4.2 Face descriptors: Implementation details

4.2.1 HOG descriptor

For a given image region (R), the HOG descriptor is computed using the following parameters: the input image region is of size 32×32 pixels ($ImSize = [32, 32]$), each cell of size 8×8 pixels ($CellSize = [8, 8]$), and the number of cells in a block 2×2 cells ($BlockSize = [2, 2]$). The local histogram corresponds to 13 orientations ($NumBins = 13$) and with no overlap between blocks. According to these parameters, the HOG descriptor is given by 208 features. This number is computed as the product of the number of blocks per image ($BlocksPerImage$) times the size of each HOG block ($BlockSize$) times the number of bins ($NumBins$).

4.2.2 COV descriptor

To construct the covariance descriptor, we start by extracting the local features that are represented in 2D maps having the same spatial grid as the original image (or image region/bloc). More precisely, we extract 20 different channels: (i) 6 channels corresponding to the color components in both

Situation	bareface	glasses	sunglasses	night bareface	nightglasses	Total
# training	16600	16587	7794	7273	7273	63491
# validation	40855	34899	25504	27231	31515	160004

Table 1: The distribution of images per situation in the training and validation sets.

Table 2: A summary of the different PML-based features descriptors and their dimensions ℓ -PMLD (See Eq. 3).

Level (ℓ)	Blocks (T)	PML-LBP	PML-HOG	PML-COV
4	30	1770	6240	6300
5	55	3245	11440	11550
6	91	5369	18928	19110

RGB and HSV spaces; (ii) 8 channels for x and y coordinates and the first and second derivative of the image intensity with respect to x and y ; (iii) 3 channels corresponding to three Local Binary Pattern images obtained by combining three different modes for 8 neighboring points at radius equal to 1. Since the number of channels used is 20, it follows that the covariance descriptor of each region is described by $(20 \times 21)/2 = 210$ features.

4.2.3 LBP descriptor

In this work, we considered the basic uniform LBP descriptor where the number of neighbors used to compute the LBP codes for each pixel was fixed to 8 on a circle of radius 1. The LBP histograms were normalized using L_2 norm. With these parameters, the size of the LBP histogram characterizing each image region is 59.

4.3 Feature extraction and feature subset selection

The size of the final descriptor characterizing a given input image is obtained concatenating all individual descriptors over the different blocks that define the PML representation. Table 2 summarizes the sizes of the final descriptors when the PML representation adopted 4, 5 and 6 levels and for three types of texture descriptors.

As a first stage of feature processing, we projected the data into a reduced space using the classical principal component analysis (PCA). Indeed,

to assess the trade off between the variance explained and the number of retained features, we considered to retain a set of principal features that give us about 85 – 95% of variance across the data sets. The result of this process is reported in Table 3. As it can be appreciated, only a few number of features are required to explain a maximum variance across the data sets. For the PML-HOG descriptor, we noticed that the number of retained features is greater than for the other two descriptors.

Situation	PML-COV	PML-HOG	PML-LBP
bareface	69	487	123
glasses	115	643	171
sunglasses	139	670	184
night bareface	67	584	161
nightglasses	85	612	203

Table 3: Number of features after performing PCA on each subset defined for a given descriptor and scenario.

4.4 Decision fusion method

In order to enhance the performance of our proposed scheme for drowsiness detection (See Fig. 2), we explored a scheme that efficiently combines the potentials of each of the descriptor reported previously. In fact, the final decision is reached by fusing the individual decisions of three SVM classifiers learned using the three descriptors. Figure 5 gives a graphical illustration of this scheme.

5 Experimental results

Table 4 reports the performance of our drowsiness detection scheme for different scenarios on the evaluation dataset. The first three columns correspond to individual scores achieved by PML-COV, PML-HOG and PML-LBP descriptors following the scheme shown in Fig.2, while the last column refers the combination of the three descriptors according to the SVM-blending strategy illustrated in Fig. 5. Comparing individual descriptors, we can see that the PML-HOG descriptor performs well in most scenarios giving an average score of 79.41% which is around 6% higher than the ones achieved by other two descriptors. This score has been slightly improved adopting the SVM-blending strategy.

Figure 5: A schematic representation of data flow for drowsiness detection using a SVM blending strategy.

In order to test the reliability of our approach, we compared the achieved results to those obtained by some recent drowsiness detection methods based on deep neural networks. In particular, we considered the following networks: 8-layered AlexNet (Krizhevsky et al., 2012), VGG-FaceNet (Parkhi et al., 2015) and FlowImageNet (Parkhi et al., 2015).

These three networks are independently fine-tuned for multi-class drowsiness classification given the following four classes: *non-drowsiness*, *drowsiness with eye blinking*, *nodding*, and *yawning*. Two different fusion strategies: independently-averaged architecture (IAA) and feature-fused architecture (FFA) were adopted. In IAA, each network provides the probability distribution for multi-class classification. The final distribution is set to average distribution from which the driver status is classified. In FFA, the features of the three networks are integrated in a transfer learning fashion. Their FC7 layer features are concatenated. These concatenated features feed an SVM classifier that classify each input image into one of the four classes.

Our proposed method aims to classify each frame in the video sequences based on the extracted features.

Table 4: Detection accuracy results (%).

Situation	PML-COV	PML-HOG	PML-LBP	Fusion
bareface	82.34	87.02	73.58	85.76
glasses	74.19	79.10	74.04	78.31
sunglasses	67.19	73.97	77.27	76.86
night bareface	79.76	83.88	78.38	83.76
nightglasses	68.90	73.10	71.00	74.52
Average	74.48	79.41	74.85	79.84

Since the ground truth labels of test dataset were not provided, we evaluated the different approaches on the evaluation dataset. We also adopted the same protocol that was depicted in (Park et al., 2017). In particular, in order to simplify the training process, the training video sequences are sub-sampled by a factor of ten.

Table 5 reports the detection rate over the evaluation set using different approaches. As it can be appreciated, the proposed scheme outperformed all individual deep CNNs. In four situations the proposed methods outperformed the fusion scheme DDD-IA, and only when Night-glasses are involved, our approach seems to perform worse than DDD-IA. Faces with glasses are challenging since the glasses seem to be a disturbing factor that can affect the goodness of the extracted descriptor.

Table 5: Detection accuracy results (%)

Situation	Alexnet	VGGFaceNet	FlowImageNet	LRCN	DDD-FFA	DDD-IA	3D DCNN	PMLDB
Bareface	70.42	63.87	56.33	68.75	79.41	69.83	75.1	85.76
Glasses	61.63	70.53	61.61	61.73	74.10	75.93	72.3	78.31
Sunglasses	70.20	57.00	67.57	71.47	61.89	69.86	70.9	76.86
Night bareface	64.69	73.75	66.82	57.39	70.27	74.93	68.4	83.76
Nightglasses	62.70	74.10	55.17	55.63	68.37	74.77	68.3	74.52
Average	65.93	67.85	61.50	62.99	70.81	73.06	71.2	79.84

<i>Alexnet</i>	<i>A Convolutional Neural Network by Alex Krizhevsky et al. (Krizhevsky et al., 2012)</i>
<i>VGGFaceNet</i>	<i>A Convolutional Neural Network by Omkar M. Parkhi et al. (Parkhi et al., 2015)</i>
<i>FlowImageNet</i>	<i>A class of Recurrent Convolutional Network where the input is a flow of images (Donahue et al., 2017)</i>
<i>LRCN</i>	<i>Long-term recurrent convolutional networks (Donahue et al., 2017)</i>
<i>DDD-FFA</i>	<i>Deep Drowsiness Detection System Based on Feature-Fused Architecture (Park et al., 2009)</i>
<i>DDD-IA</i>	<i>Deep Drowsiness Detection System Based on Independently-Averaged Architecture (Park et al., 2009)</i>
<i>3D DCNN</i>	<i>3D-Deep Convolutional Neural Network (Yu et al., 2017)</i>
<i>PMLDB</i>	<i>Our proposed PML-based descriptors with Decision blending</i>

6 Conclusion

Vision-based driver fatigue monitoring can be useful for many advanced systems. One of the main challenges is to retrieve effective features from face images. In this paper, multi-scale and multi-block features are used to retrieve drowsiness features from the whole face, overcoming the drawback of missing some important and useful indicators when focusing only on the eyes or the mouth. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed face descriptor can be equal or superior to several existing approaches that are based on deep Convolutional Neural Nets.

Experimental results show that the proposed approach has about 80% detection accuracy on NTHU-drowsy driver detection benchmark dataset. Future work envisions the use of dynamic descriptors.

Compliance with ethical standards

The authors declare that the studies conducted comply with the ethical standards.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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